

1 **NLRP4 is an oocyte-specific NLR.**

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7 We recently discovered a cycling-based sensor function for NLRP10 in detection of high cellular speed,
8 and identified a cell cycle-centric interaction between NOD2 and the p53 regulatory pathway through
9 ligase Mdm4. We report here an essential and basic function for NLR receptors in the reproductive
10 system. Here, the sensor *NLRP4* was enriched in the human oocyte at meiosis II.

11 Citations

- 12
- 13 1. Mamoor, S., Control of MDM4 by NOD2. 2023.
 - 14 2. Mamoor, S. NLRP10 is a transcriptional sensor of cellular activity associated with high speed.
15 2023.
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